
Physicochemical Studies Of Soil From Some Farms Of Zari Region For Plant Growth And Soil Management

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Abstract:

To development quality in the soil physicochemical analysis is very important. The physicochemical study of territory is very significant because both physical and chemical properties which bear upon the soil productivity. Soil is an important component of our farming. The availability of water and quality of soil are very important factor for the good productivity and yield of the crop. The present work has been carried out to study some parameters of soil samples collected from Zari Taluka, District Yavatmal, Maharashtra. The soil characterization was carried out for the parameters like pH, Conductivity, TDS, organic carbon, available nitrate nitrogen, calcium and magnesium. In this paper there is studies of variation parameters due to the soil quality in different farms of Gawara, Kamalvelli, Satpalli and Surdapur

Keywords: Parameters, pH, Conductivity, TDS.

Introduction:

Traditional methods of soil analysis often involve laboratory intensive processes and can be time-consuming, limiting their practicality for large-scale agricultural operations. In soil management there is use of this parameter for better soil management practices for increasing the plant growth and agricultural production. For this purposed testing of soil are very important for good implement of soil. Chemical and physical analysis of different types of soil in india¹ Effect of colloidal particle size on physicochemical properties and aggregation behaviors of two alkaline soils² In this paper some method which are applicable for farmer to increases the quality of soil. Some selected soil sample from Viroda is a town in Burhanpur district of India state of Madhya pradesh. Mostly agricultural crops is found in Viroda village is as follows

Banana, Cotton, Maize, Wheat, Jawar, and Haldi. Banana is one of the most important crops in Viroda village³ Exploring the influence of land use types on soil properties at arjo-dhidhessa sugar estate, western ethiopia⁴ Release kinetics of boron in acidic soils as affected by calcium form different sources⁵. The effects of various land use types on particular physicochemical characteristics of the soil in mante watershed, south regional government of ethiopia⁶. This reseach paper the used soil is in different farms of Gawara, Kamalvelli, Satpalli and Surdapur village of Zari taluka region, this soil is not getting polluted due to no industrial waste problem in this region. All samples were collected in winter season. Analysis of soil in carried out for the studies of various parameters like pH. Conductivity, TDS, Organic Carbon, Available Nitrate Nitrogen, Calcium and Magnesium.

Material and Methodology:

We collect soil sample as per the requirement of farmer. The soil samples were collected from different village of Zari Taluka at Yavatmal District in state Maharashtra at the time of month November-December 2024 from different

sampling stations. Soil samples V_1 , V_2 , V_3 and V_4 were collected in the depth of 0-30 cm from the surface of soil from Gawara, Kamalvelli, Satpalli and Surdapur villages were collected for analysis⁷ as shown in the Table 1.

Table 1: Soil samples from different sampling stations

Name of Village	Gawara	Kamalvelli	Satpalli	Surdapur
Sample Site	V_1	V_2	V_3	V_4

The soil samples were preserved in polythene bags for further analysis⁸. The chemicals and reagents used for analysis were of A. R. grade. Method used for Estimation of parameters physicochemical

analysis were carried out in the laboratory of department of chemistry, collage of Engineering & Technology District, Akola, (M.S), India, are shown in the Table 2

Table 2: Method used for Estimation of Some Parameters.

S.N.	Parameter	Method
1	Colour	By viewing Soil
2	Moisture	By weighing
3	pH	pH-Metry
4	Conductivity	Conductometry
5	Available Nitrate Nitrogen	Titration
6	Alkalinity	Titration
7	Total Dissolved Solid	TDS Metry
8	Organic Carbon	Titration
9	Calcium	Titration
10	Magnesium	Titration

Result and Discussion:

Physicochemical parameters just like a Colour, Moisture, pH, Conductivity, Alkalinity, Total Dissolved Solid, Organic Carbon, Calcium and Magnesium of soil samples^{9,10} presented in Table 3.

Colour: In the earth soil there is lot of colour soil sample but some presented Soil samples are V_1 , V_2 , V_3 and V_4 are brown and black in colour.

Moisture: The moisture content value ranges from 17.15% to 21.10% It is clear from result sample V_3 have highest moisture content than samples V_1 , V_2 , V_3 , V_4 and V_5 .

pH: The pH of soil is one of the most important physicochemical Parameter. It affects minerals nutrient soil quality and

much microorganism activity. The pH was observed in the ranges from 6.9 to 8.2 The samples V_1 and V_3 are very slightly alkaline and samples V_2 and V_4 are medium alkaline.

Conductivity: The measurement of conductivity is for measure the current that given a clear idea of soluble salt present in the soil. conductivity depends upon the dilution of soil suspension. The conductivity vales range from $0.18 \mu S$ to $0.46 \mu S$. Conductivity of sample V_3 is less as compared to samples V_1 , V_2 and V_4 .

Available Nitrate Nitrogen: Available nitrate nitrogen in the soil from 290 to 410 kg/hectare. The soil sample V_4 has high nitrate nitrogen as compared to samples V_1 , V_2 , V_3 .

Alkalinity: Alkalinity was observed in the ranges from 198% to 561% Alkalinity of sample V₂ is less as compare to samples V₁, V₃ and V₄.

Total Dissolved Solid (TDS): TDS values for soil sample ranges from 209 to 376 Soil sample V₁ has lowest TDS as compared to V₂, V₃, and V₄.

Organic Carbon: Organic carbon is the index for nitrogen content in the soil. The source of organic carbon in the cultivated soil included crop residue, animal manure, cover crops, green manure and organic

fertilizer etc. Organic carbon values range from 0.16% to 0.28% Organic carbon of sample V₄, is high as compared to samples V₁, V₂, and V₃.

Calcium: Calcium ranges from 400ml/100gm to 420ml/100gm Soil sample V₄ have high calcium content as compared to samples V₁, V₂, and V₃.

Magnesium: Magnesium available to plants as the ions Mg²⁺ its content in the soil samples ranges from 8ml/100gm to 42ml/100gm. Sample V₁, contains less amount of magnesium

Table 3: Physicochemical parameters of Soil sample

S.N.	Soil Parameters	V ₁	V ₂	V ₃	V ₄	IAS Soil Analysis
1	Colour	Brown	Black	Black	Black	Visual Assessment
2	Moisture (%)	17.15	18.02	18.96	21.10	17-30% Per Crop
3	pH	7.3	7.6	7.8	7.9	7.0 -8.0
4	Conductivity	0.48	0.38	0.15	0.31	< 0.8 Ds/M
5	ANN (kg/ha)	388	407	295	409	Variable
6	Alkalinity (%)	214	190	361	568	Variable
7	TDS	307	376	345	288	< 1000 PPM
8	Organic Carbon (%)	0.17	0.15	0.19	0.28	0.1-3%
9	Calcium (ml/100gm)	412	418	406	419	Variable
10	Magnesium (mg/100gm)	09	08	07	08	Variable

[IAS- Agriculture Standard, ANN-Available Nitrate Nitrofen, TDS-Total Dissolve Solid.]

Conclusion:

In fertilizers containing magnesium and calcium are added for the proper growth and development of the crop. On the basis of this study farmers can be get various idea about the fertilizers and nutrients needed to soil for increase the percentage yield of crops. From all conclusion physicochemical analysis of soil different values for various farms.

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